

ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT AND ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR: A REVIEW OF RESEARCH

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Abstract

The existence of committed employees is among the most important and leading factor determining the success of an organisation especially in the present day competitive and a volatile business environment. These employees not only perform their duties well but also go beyond their responsibilities and freely give off their time and energy to succeed at the assigned job. Such behaviours are neither prescribed nor required; yet are of paramount importance for the smooth functioning of the organization. It is in view of this profound importance, understanding the nature and sources of OCB has long been a continued priority for organizational researchers (Organ, 1988) and remains so. However, the purpose of this study is to provide an up-to-date, integrative and comprehensive review on the relationship between the organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour and also to make an important contribution to extant literature on the relationship between the above mentioned constructs.

Keywords: organisational commitment, OCB

Introduction

Organizations exist around us in different forms and shape our lives. Organizations are social entities composed of people and their relationships. Organisations have had a great respect for efficiency/effectiveness and have been the subject matter of a number of bestselling books like *Theory Z*, *In search of Excellence*, *The Change Masters* and *Wealth of Nations*. Contemporary organisations on the one hand generally seek to be effective and on the other hand face multiple expectations from within and outside. In order to achieve a desired level of performance, organisations resort to restructuring, mergers and introduce competitive staff benefits. Despite the attempts, organisations still look for various ways and means to be effective. Echoing the concern Katz (1964) notes that organisations to be effective need to retain employees within their systems and argues that it can be done through organisational commitment, “ a psychological state that binds the individual to the organisation”, (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

Organ (1988) views OCB as one of the discretionary behaviour which has been identified as being linked to organisational commitment. Certifying the link Chang et.al (2010) claim that organisational commitment provides higher chances of developing organisational citizenship behaviour among employees and Organ (1988) suggested that higher levels of OCB lead to a more efficient organisation and help bring new resources in the organisation. Organ (1988) defines OCB as individual behaviour that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly, recognised by the formal reward system, and that in aggregate promotes the effective performance of the organisation.

1.1 Organisational commitment

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The concept of organizational commitment derives from an article “The organization Man” written by Whyte in 1956. From 1960 till now organizational commitment has gone through four different periods but not very different contextually. The evolution period of organizational commitment is fifty years initialized with the Side-bet theory of Becker in 1960; subsequently an affective dependence theory was put forward by Porter in 1974. And since then, an extensive amount of research has been put forward by academic scholars to develop an understanding of organizational commitment and its dimensions in order to fulfil the managerial desires to have a devoted staff so that a high organizational performance can be achieved.

Although, there are many conceptualisations of organisational commitment in literature, but the most widely accredited and popular approach of defining and explaining organisational commitment is of Meyer and his associates. Allen and Meyer (1990) focused on three dimensions/facets of organizational commitment that are affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment.

Meyer and Allen (1984) defined affective commitment as “positive feelings of identification with, attachment to and involvement in the work organisation”, continuance commitment as “the extent to which employees feel committed to their organisation by virtue of the costs that they feel are associated with leaving”. Allen and Meyer (1990) define normative commitment as “the employee’s feelings of obligation to remain with the organisation”. Consequently, the concept of organisational commitment is described as a tri-dimensional concept, characterised by the affective, continuance and normative dimensions (Meyer & Allen, 1990). These three components describe three psychological states which reflect want, need and ought or obligation (Allen & Myer, 1990). Employees who possess high affective commitment stay the part of organization because they “wish for”, individuals with high normative commitment stay the part of organization because of feeling which tend them “ought to do so”, and lastly employees with high continuance commitment stay the part of organization for the reason “that they need to” (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

The significance and importance of the concept of organizational commitment in terms of leading to beneficial organizational and desirable outcomes such as increased effectiveness, reduced absenteeism and turnover, has been documented by many studies such as those of Steers (1977); Porter et al. (1974); Reiches (1985) and Tett and Meyer (1993). Organizational Commitment not only makes an employee to stay in the organization but also make it possible for the employees to take part in organizational activities (Steyrer, et al, 2008). According to Chang et al(2010) if organizations become successful in keeping its employees committed to the organization; there is a higher chance of developing OCB among employees.

1.2 Organisational Citizenship Behaviour

Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is referred to as a set of discretionary workplace behaviours that exceed one’s basic job requirements. They are often described as behaviours that go beyond the call of duty. Research on OCB has been extensive since its introduction nearly thirty years back (Bateman & Organ, 1983). Organizational citizenship behaviour has been defined in the literature as a multidimensional concept that includes all positive organizationally relevant behaviours of organizational members including traditional in role behaviours, organizationally pertinent extra-role behaviours, and political behaviours, such as full and responsible organizational participation (Dyne et. al 1994).

In 1983, Dennis Organ and his colleagues were first to coin the term Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) (Bateman & Organ, 1983; Smith, Organ & Near, 1983). Drawing on Chester Bernard’s concept (Barnard, 1938) of the “willingness to co-operate” and Daniel Katz’s (Katz, 1964; Katz & Kahn, 1966, 1978) distinction between dependable role performance and innovative and spontaneous behaviours, Organ (1988) defined OCB as individual behaviour that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly, recognised by the formal reward system, and that in aggregate promotes the effective performance of the organisation. Moreover, Organ (1988) identified five distinct dimensions of OCB: *Altruism* (helping specific others); *civic virtue* (keeping up with important matters within the organisation); *conscientiousness* (compliance with norms); *courtesy* (consulting others before taking action); and *sportsmanship* (not complaining about trivial matters).

2. Organisational commitment and Organisational citizenship behaviour

There are major groups of antecedents of OCB that have been emphasized in studies of different researchers. Among the antecedents of the OCB, organizational commitment is said to be the strong one (Khan & Rashid, 2012). According to LePine et. al., (2002), organizational commitment is one of the strong predictors of OCB.

An employee's organizational commitment is positively related to organizational citizenship behaviour (O'Reilly and Chatman, 1986). It is therefore necessary to define the likely relationship between organisational commitment and OCB and the extent to which it is prevalent in organisational processes. Emphasizing the importance of relationship between organisational commitment and OCB, Ahmadi & Avajian (2011) attempted to explore the structure of, and casual relationships between the two constructs in a socio-cultural context in Iran. The analysis of the data revealed that both affective and normative commitment were found to be significant predictors of both OCB components, i.e., altruism and compliance; however, continuance commitment was unrelated to altruism and negatively associated with compliance. In a similar fashion, Bakshi et al (2011) conducted a study aimed at exploring the linkages between three component model of organisational commitment proposed by Allen & Meyer (1991) and OCB as defined by Organ (1988). The results of the study suggested that only normative commitment predicts the OCB to some extent, but the impact of affective and continuance commitment on aggregate measure of OCB was found to be insignificant.

Huang & You (2011) adopted the three components of organisational commitment scale of Allen & Meyer (1991) and followed the suggestions of William & Anderson (1991) to explore the influence of the three components of organisational commitment on in-role behaviours and two dimensions of OCB, i.e., OCBI & OCBO; affective commitment revealed significant influence on two dimensions of OCB (OCBI & OCBO), however, it does not show significant influence on in-role behaviours. Secondly, this study found that the continuance commitment has significantly negative influence on in-role behaviours and OCBI; however, it does not have significant influence on OCBO. Further, findings of the study show that normative commitment has significant influence on IRB & OCBO; however, it does not have significant influence on OCBI. Allameh et. al., (2011) investigated the relationship between organisational commitment and OCB. However, the findings of the study resulted in refusing the existence of relationship between components of organisational commitment and OCB dimensions.

In an effort to extend the literature of OCB via an examination of the correlations among organisational commitment, job satisfaction and OCB, Sesan & Basim (2012) revealed that job satisfaction and organisational commitment has a significant impact on OCB and that organisational commitment had a mediating role in the relation between job satisfaction and OCB. Baig et. al (2012) investigated the nature of, strength, predictive value and significance of the unique associations of organisational commitment with procedural justice, participation in decision making and OCB of school teachers. The results of the statistical analysis substantiate that both participation and procedural justice had a strong influence on organisational commitment. However, procedural justice has a slightly strong correlation with organisational commitment than participation in decision making. Specifically, results suggested that organisational commitment and OCB are not only positively and significantly correlated but organisational commitment can also account for reasonable amount of variation in OCB as a single factor.

Chang et. al (2011) conducted a study to examine the relationship between OCBs, organisational commitment and organisational learning effects. The findings of the study revealed that the effects of organisational learning are influenced by the OCBs and organisational commitment positively and that the organisational commitments can influence OCBs positively.

Aslam (2012) studied the relationship of OCB with job satisfaction, organisational commitment and turnover intentions and found OCB to be positively correlated with

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organisational commitment and job satisfaction while relationship between OCB and turnover intentions was found to be weak, insignificant and negative. Qamar (2012) explored

the relationship of the antecedents of job satisfaction and organisational commitment with the dimensions of organisational citizenship behaviour in the banking sector of Pakistan. The

research findings revealed that organisational commitment appears to be more strongly related to all the dimensions of OCB while as job satisfaction has moderate yet positive relationship with OCB.

Sjahrudin et. al., (2013) in their study to explore the relationship between organisational justice and OCB mediated by trust in manager and organisational commitment discovered that organisational justice, trust and commitment are deciding factors to increase OCB. Further, high organisational justice has no significant direct effect to increase OCB in positive direction, but with the mediation of trust in managers and organisational commitment, organisational justice significantly increases OCB. Mirabizaden & Ghetaisi (2012) investigated the relative importance of educational opportunities, work-life policies and empowerment activities on organisational commitment influencing OCB accordingly. The results of their study indicated that educational opportunities, work-life policies and empowerment practices have strong positive relationship with organisational commitment which eventually yields an improvement on OCB.

Conclusion

The present study was an attempt to find the relationship between the dimensions of organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour. Some important findings of the study are that only affective and normative commitment dimensions of organisational commitment were found to be positively and significantly correlated with OCB; continuance commitment was found to be unrelated with OCB, whereas few studies have refused the existence of any such relationship. Moreover, it was found that job satisfaction and organisational commitment had a significant impact on OCB wherein organisational commitment had a mediating role in the relation between job satisfaction and organisational commitment. Through review of extant literature on organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour, it was also found that certain factors like educational opportunities, work-life policy, empowerment practices, trust in managers, organisational justice, transformational leadership and job satisfaction have strong relationship with organisational commitment which eventually can account for reasonable amount of variation in OCB.

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